

OPPORTUNITIES FOR OPEN LEARNING IN TVET

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ABSTRACT

Despite proficiency in many technical fields, many TVET providers tend to be slow to adopt open learning principles and methodologies within their practice. This short article hopes to argue the case for the many opportunities open learning can bring to TVET students and institutions.

Keywords: *TVET, Open learning, online learning, VOOCs*

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, many Technical, Vocational Education and Training (TVET) providers have shied away from offering open learning opportunities arguing that learning online defeats the purpose of a vocational education which is typically hands-on in nature. Another common complaint is that it would require a huge financial investment to create interactive learning that can meet the demanding needs of today's VET industries. Open learning encompasses activities that broaden or enhance learning opportunities within or without formal education (D'Antoni, 2009). There are many definitions of open learning, but broadly, open learning allows learners the flexibility to choose how they learn from a choice of time, location, instructional modes, accessibility, and other factors affecting the learning process (Caliskan, 2012). This article looks at opportunities presented by open learning methodologies and modes for TVET.

Challenges faced by TVET Providers

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 seeks to increase access to general and technical and vocational education at all levels for all people. Yet, in 2018, nearly 260 million youths and children were out of formal education (UNESCO, 2020). To tackle this, it is necessary to increase availability, accessibility, and acceptability in TVET provision. In general, TVET has an inferior reputation to higher education and is consistently seen as the lesser option (or the last resort) for students who wish to pursue a post-secondary academic path. This negative perception affects parents and their children's motivation and decision-making and is particularly common in developing countries (Tlapana & Myeki, 2020). As university fees soar, TVET provision is being increasingly seen as the only affordable educational option. In turn, the same perception of TVET being a lesser option at government-level means more funding is given to higher education institutions rather than TVET providers (Hanni, 2019). As a result, TVET providers and schools generally are less likely to have the expertise, resources, or finances to develop, acquire necessary equipment and/or implement open learning within their environments.

Learners from socially and economically disadvantaged backgrounds tend to be overrepresented in vocational education and therefore are less likely to have access to the internet or to a personal computer, or to receive support from their parents (ILO-UNESCO-WBG, 2020). To a certain extent, Western European countries have had some success in trying to reframe TVET attractiveness as the development of different dimensions of humanity (Winch, 2013). In fact, the French educational system recognises that individuals should be prepared for their roles as economically active workers as well as democratic citizens (Méhaut, 2011).

In research conducted in 2022, challenges to implementing open learning methodologies may also come from TVET teaching staff. While 100% of male teachers used computers in their teaching practice, only 50% female teachers used ICT-based tools and resources. Nearly 70% of teachers aged 25 or under were highly proficient in the use of technology in their teaching

practice, while only 30% of teachers aged 51 and older demonstrated the same level of proficiency (Ainutdinova, Tregubova, Ng, & Kopnov, 2022).

Moreover, many teachers are unaware of changing pedagogies in terms of open education compared to when students are seated in front of teachers in a physical classroom. For open learning to be effective, the online components must move away from the idea of simply using the internet webspace as a repository for documents (and indeed, PowerPoints). A collection of links of documents to download is merely that – it is not an instructional tool, nor does it efficiently engage with students.

Classrooms that moved to Zoom, Microsoft Teams or similar platforms ran up against a host of issues ranging from privacy concerns to student apathy or fatigue from information overload (Murphy & Waters, 2022; Ebarido, Padagas, & Trapero, 2021). In the latter, it was most certainly due to the inability or ineffectiveness of teachers to engage with their students. Many teachers were left to discover by themselves ways of using technology and software and designing lessons for online delivery without the necessary support from their school management. Research has shown that teachers were woefully under-prepared for this (Scherer, Howard, Tondeur, & Siddiq, 2021). This shows that not all teachers are prepared to design open learning possibilities for their students.

Opportunities for Open Learning.

The COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns forced many TVET providers to reconsider their delivery options for continuity's sake. Many governments and companies have understood the importance of open learning and have thus provided support for this. However, often the education providers rushed to create online courses without having enough time to consider pedagogy, delivery methodology, content, student engagement, and assessment.

During the lockdowns resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, there were three main approaches adopted by education authorities to maintain educational delivery at a distance:

1. Direct Government intervention/control
2. Agency intervention
3. Individual response

Direct government intervention refers to top-down decision-making where national-level policies are implemented about what solutions and methodologies will be used to implement open learning. Countries that have done so include Turkey, Serbia, Georgia, and Egypt which have overseen or prescribed the technological solutions, and national content creation and dissemination (ETF, 2020). In most countries, the ministries of education have played a vital role in empowering technological companies such as broadcasters and those in telecommunications, liaising with donors, and accelerating the provision of open learning possibilities. A few countries, mainly those in the Caucasus region, immediately authorised

additional spending on education during the pandemic. Some countries went as far as prescribing lessons, platforms, and software.

In other countries, governments assigned responsibility for open learning to **regional authorities and agencies** as a method of multiplying control at a more local level. For example, prior to the recent war, Ukraine adopted a decentralised bottom-up model for its TVET education whereby open learning was implemented by TVET institutions, with the backing of regional training methodological centres. Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan did the same regionally, also.

However, in much of Western Europe and even countries like Israel, it was the **individual schools and teachers** who were entrusted with the delivery of open learning based on virtual classrooms, online projects and fostering a closer connection with students and parents. Moldova took the opportunity to test out its TVET reform by requiring institutions to ensure access for students to online learning platforms. TVET providers were requested to conduct remote competence assessment through the creation of a digital portfolio and the completion of an online project (ETF, 2020).

Post COVID lockdowns, research has shown that there is an appetite on the part of students to continue with open learning methods (e.g. at least 84% of students surveyed in Korea). Conversely, the same study showed that only 14% of the teachers wanted to resume in this manner (Kim, Myung, Yoon, Moon, Ryu, & Yim, 2020). In India, 54% of students wanted online learning to continue, but 24% wanted to return to normal classes (Gupta, Dabas, Swarnim, & Mishra, 2021). A United Kingdom survey found that teachers' workloads had increased substantially but less than 50% of teachers felt confident with teaching online (apart from the 76% of Computer Science teachers who felt calmly capable of doing so) (Watermeyer, Crick, Knight, & Goodal, 2021).

What this shows is that there remain many opportunities for open learning in the world of TVET. There may be opportunities in refining the way we create open learning courses, improving the pedagogy behind these courses, changing the mindset of students and educators vis-à-vis open learning, looking at more effective ways of assessing learning, and increasing the flexibility in utilising different modes of learning within one course.

Moreover, the open learning nature allows institutions to attract experts and international speakers from around the world without the expense and hassle of organising international air travel. It allows students in geographically-diverse locations to access the same resources and opportunities, regardless of reason or circumstance, often at their own time and pace. Many platforms have also evolved to include various collaborative features such as interactive virtual whiteboards, breakout rooms, polls and post-it notes that can be launched with a click of a mouse for synchronous classes. These are easy to set up and implement, and the most basic instruments often come with measurement tools.

It is important to point out that open learning is not strictly online only learning. It is more akin to the term 'blended learning,' where online learning tools are combined with face-to-face learning to supplement or enhance the learning, rather than replace face-to-face learning.

Hannay and Newvine (2006) suggest that e-learning alone is not enough and that the finest features of distance learning should be assimilated into the traditional courses to create a 'hybrid' educational environment. These same findings indicate that students prefer online education opportunities because in general it allows them to manage their commitments more conveniently.

In the Pro-VET project, four Russian universities and four Serbian universities carried out research among their stakeholder networks focusing on TVET teachers' readiness to carry out online or open learning. The National Roadmap for the Sustainable Professional Development of VET Teachers in Serbia was drafted as a result of this project (Papic-Blagojevic, 2022). It provides a national-level approach towards getting TVET providers and their teachers ready for modern challenges in teaching and learning, including the need to understand open learning principles and methodologies. Seven Vocational Open Online Courses (VOOCs) were created in Serbia and Russia to help teachers develop themselves professionally by first undergoing some open learning themselves. It allows them to change their own mindsets about online modalities. The roadmap itself is such a success that even one of the VOOCs has been accredited by the Serbian Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development paving the way for the recognition of similar VOOCs.

CONCLUSION

As open learning was a lesser-explored option prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the range of possibilities offered by this mode is now wide open. Given that TVET providers no longer have an excuse to avoid open learning principles and methodologies, it is expected that the coming years will lead to an explosion of open learning opportunities. TVET institutions have the chance to stay ahead of the curve, not follow it.

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